

Biological Resources Certifications Schemes

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Type

- R** Document report
- DEM** Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
- DEC** Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.
- OTHER**

Dissemination Level

- PU** Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN** Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- CI** Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 1001/844/EC

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Report

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1 Publishable Executive Summary

BioReCer aims to ensure the environmental performance and traceability of biological feedstock used by the bio-based industries. This will be executed through the deployment of guidelines to strengthen current certification schemes by including new criteria that align with EU taxonomy and EU corporate due diligence regulations. Within this approach, the added value, the use, as well as the social acceptance of bioproducts will be increased.

The BioReCer website serves as the main communication instrument for the project and provides a quick and broad overview of the project objectives, progress and results to all interested stakeholders and the general public. It further provides an application form for the BioResources Stakeholders Platform (BRSP).

All presented content follows the objectives to increase the project reach, to recruit stakeholders for the BRSP, to accelerate the adaptation of certification schemes and to structure and highlight project related activities.

2 Website

The website is available under <https://biorecer.eu> and will remain frequently updated throughout the project duration. All website texts informing about the project and the BRSP were created under the lead of nova-Institut with contributions and feedback of the entire BioReCer consortium. General content and the website structure were discussed in the first months of the project and agreed upon by all partners.

The website includes an application form for the BRSP, which will provide access to the BioReCer ICT Tool (BIT) and link to all project related publications and public deliverables. Additional downloadable content will include the project video, the project flyer and the BioReCer infographic, policy briefs and finally the guidelines for adaptation of certification schemes.

The website is hosted and maintained by nova-Institut with support of the project coordinator Cetaqua. The official website launch took place at the 8th of February and equals deliverable **D8.2** of the BioReCer project (due date end of M6).

This website is based on the open-source software WordPress (<https://wordpress.org>), which is a content management system (CMS) that guarantees a long-term availability of up-to-date features that can be accessed without any hurdles. It is user-friendly and receives updates and technical support from a big international community of users and programmers. The website will remain available for five years after the project ends in order to make the project results accessible for the public.

Figure 1: BioReCer website structure (excerpt from the front page with icons)

2.1 Website Structure

The website menu consists of several subpages. By clicking the subpage title in the menu item, the website automatically jumps to the selected subcategory on the respective page. The initial website menu includes the following elements and might be adjusted in the future according to the project requirements:

1. Home (front page)

- a. Sliders with graphical material (partly provided by the consortium, partly stock photos)
- b. General information on the project (run-time, budget, stakeholders, etc.) with icons
- c. Introduction of the project with its objectives, specific goals, technological pillars, etc. including graphical elements and buttons to switch to paragraphs on BRIE-LL, the case studies and the BRSP on other subpages
- d. Funding statement
- e. A slider for registration for the BioReCer newsletter

2. Project

- a. Current situation, problems and solutions
- b. Description of BRIE-LL (including BIT)
- c. Detailed information on the four case studies (with icons and pictures)

3. Work packages and their objectives as accordion

4. Consortium

- a. information on each partner including partner logos and link to the respective webpage

5. BRSP

- a. Header for promotion of upcoming events
- b. Short description of the function/tasks/goals/activities of the BRSP
- c. Links/buttons to application form and – as soon as it is available - to BIT
- d. Overview of planned participatory group activities

6. BRSP membership form

- a. Registration with name/institution/email address/country
- b. Check-boxes for interest in case studies
- c. Check-boxes for stakeholder type of the applying member (e.g. biomass producer, standardisation body, consumer association)

7. News & Media

- a. Downloadable material (e.g. infographic/brochure)
- b. Overview on planned workshops
- c. Press releases
- d. Public deliverables
- e. Publications

8. Contact

- a. Information of the project coordinator, the persons in charge of communication activities and BRSP member management.
- b. A slider for registration for the BioReCer newsletter

2.2 Website Content

The website provides a comprehensive overview over the project’s objectives as well as the goals and objectives of the single work packages and case studies. It also informs on the three technological pillars and the two levels of interaction (digital and remote) upon which the project is based.

Figure 2: Layout for the four case-studies (excerpt)

An infographic created with input from the entire consortium allows a simplified and visualised easy understanding of the different objectives and key elements of BioReCer and is available on the website.

Figure 3: BioReCer frontpage and infographic

Furthermore, the website will serve as a tool to inform and motivate stakeholders to join the BRSP, which is the essential central and physical level of the project’s BRIE-LL. It will also link to BIT which serves as the digital level of the BRIE-LL.

A subpage introduces all project partners with a short profile and external links to their institutions’ websites.

Figure 4: BioReCer consortium information

A dedicated publication and public deliverables section on the “News & Media” subpage provides access to all project related publications (including policy briefs and guidelines) and hereby actively supports the open access requirements of the European commission.

Figure 5: BioReCer News & Media subpage

A funding statement and logo of the European Union in the website footer inform visitors about the grant agreement number and the related funding agreement.

Figure 6: EU funding statement

2.3 BRSP-Membership

BioReCer is based on intense stakeholder involvement and follows the goal to create a strong and interactive stakeholder network. The website therefore includes an application form for the BRSP, where interested stakeholders can get in touch and become members.

Become a Stakeholder/BRSP Member

The image shows a screenshot of the BioReCer website's BRSP membership page. The page has a dark blue background. At the top, it says "Become a Stakeholder/BRSP Member". Below this, there is a light blue box on the left with the text "First Stakeholder Training Action" and "To be announced". To the right of this box is a photograph of a group of people sitting around a long table in a meeting room. Below the photograph is a white button with the text "START BRSP MEMBERSHIP". At the bottom of the page, there is a section titled "What is the BRSP" with two paragraphs of text explaining the BRSP's purpose and how it will be implemented.

Figure 7: BioReCer BRSP

Home Project Work Packages Consortium BRSP News & Media
Contact

Stakeholder registration

Name

Institution

Email address

Country

In which of the four case studies are you interested in?

- Case Study 1 - Fish Cannery Industry and Wastewater Treatment Sludge in Galicia (Spain)
- Case Study 2 - Urban waste in Lombardia (Italy)
- Case Study 3 - Agricultural waste in the Region of Central Macedonia (Greece)
- Case Study 4 - Residues from the forest industry in Västernorrland (Sweden)

I wish to engage with BIORECER stakeholders as
(Select the option that most applies to you and in context to the type of input you feel most comfortable giving to the project)

Figure 8: BRSP membership form (excerpt)

3 Conclusion

The website will be updated with further downloadable material, information on project progress and results, information on the case studies (eventually including an additional international study), publications, photos and graphical material as well as the link to BIT after its successful establishment.

If required, the website will be adjusted in order to recruit more members and to better suit the needs of the BRSP.

Since only few consortium members provided image material, the website mainly includes purchased stock photos. Throughout the project duration these stock photos will be replaced with photo material generated by the consortium.

The deliverable **D8.2** was created by NOVA with ongoing support and feedback of the entire BioReCer consortium and submitted in time.

4 List of Abbreviations

BioReCer	Biological Resources Certifications Schemes
BIT	BioReCer ICT Tool
BRIE-LL	BioReCer Innovation Ecosystem Living Lab
BRSP	BioResources Stakeholders Platform
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union